

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS SPEAKING SKILLS THROUGH THE INTEREST TO THE CULTURE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES

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***Abstract:** In the given article the improvement of students speaking skills via the interest to the overseas culture are described. The importance of development of English language through the cultural communication opportunities.*

***Keywords:** cultural communication, intercultural communication, culture of foreign countries, English language, Communicative Language Teaching Approach*

It is important to emphasize that intercultural communication is of great importance in the cultural life of all developed countries, where globalization processes are rapidly increasing. The motivation for encouraging students is to engage in activities in the process of cultural communication, having conversation with tourists visiting the country, meetings with businessmen, participants in international scientific conferences and diplomatic discussions, entrepreneurs and employees, which prove the importance of the English language in cultural communication.

It is not a secret that linguists are currently focusing on the benefits of more effectively teaching intercultural communicative competence by making students interested in the language culture of the target country.

Figure 1. Structural framework of intercultural communication competencies

Definitely, increasing intercultural communicative competence shows the importance of teaching English as a language of communication, the interdependence of a foreign language and foreign culture, as well as intercultural understanding as the goal of the Communicative Language Teaching Approach. It is the competence that allows students to prepare for life in a multicultural world and supports them.

Along with language competence, the importance of developing intercultural communicative competence requires in meeting the modern requirements for students to acquire the intercultural communication skills, since in the process they may encounter language and cultural barriers. With this approach, it is necessary to understand cultural consciousness, cultural worldview and behavior, as well as understand the representatives of other cultures and be able to socialize with them.

Undeniably, culture plays an incomparable role in the development of students' speaking skills by making them interested in the cultures of foreign countries. The culture of foreign countries is a very complex phenomenon, a complex system of concepts, views, values, beliefs, customs, behavior and rituals. It represents the close connection between the life, the customs and traditions, language and culture that make up this cultural concept. A foreign language and a foreign culture are not separate concepts, they support each other and develop simultaneously.

Moreover, intercultural communicative competence refers to the ability to provide shared understanding to people with different social identities. Based on the concept, cultural learning is defined as the process of acquiring cultural knowledge and skills necessary to communicate effectively with members of other cultures and establish international relations.

Figure 2. Structure of cultural consciousness

By getting students interested in foreign cultures, development of their ability to communicate in English, encouraging them to look for similarities and differences between national and international cultures. In fact, much of our foreign cultural knowledge is invisible and unconsciously used in our everyday interactions. Shifting from a traditional to an intercultural approach to English language and reading activities will help students and teachers in their professional development.

The rapid growth of student learning of English has stimulated the development of intercultural communication as well as students need to identify conflicts between different cultures in order to engage in communication and act confidently in mutual cooperation.

The most important condition for the formation of secondary linguistic qualities of students' personality is teaching language and culture in inextricable unity. Mastering the mechanisms of social and cultural norms of communication in English allows students to become a participant in adequate social relations with speakers of other linguistic and cultural communities.

In general, new directions of ongoing linguistic research are focused not only on describing language as a system, but also, first of all, on improving the mechanism of language, its cognitive and social functions. To achieve this, it forms a new paradigm - cognitive linguistics, the theory of speech acts, discursive interpretation and the theory of speech activity.

In conclusion, it can be noted that the content of foreign cultural information presented in practical classes is based on newspapers, electronic media, magazines, political speeches, literature and advertising, as well as on the interest of students in teaching English via the interest to foreign culture.

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